

Cognisynth: A Study of Multimodal Capabilities in Translation and Image Generation

Sreerag K U

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, India
sreeragku2024b@mca.ajce.in

Binumon Joseph

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, India
binumonjosephk@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— This research article discusses the multimodal application of Transformer Neural Networks (TNN) for translation and image creation. Specifically, it investigates TNNs in three applications: translation, stable diffusion for text-to-image modeling, and image-to-image generation. The study employs a TNN-based encoder-decoder framework to have this done and estimates the training loss and effectiveness of the model for custom inputs. The architecture presented in the article relies on an encoder-decoder pipeline from U-NET which compresses input texts or images and, subsequently, decodes them to generate noise-reduced images for text-to-image and image-to-image generation. The results indicate that the model is capable of creating the desired images from text prompts as well as from images. The paper in the end explores the possibility of a web application to permit the input of a text and further use all these facilities and obtain translating titles and images corresponding to the input. In that way, this study thus furthers the knowledge about TNNs in a multimodal context providing prospects for future investigation in this direction.

Keywords: Transformer neural networks, TNN, translation, stable diffusion, text-to-image generation, image-to-image generation, encoder-decoder architecture, diffusion models, UNET, DDPM, CLIP

I. INTRODUCTION

Transformer Neural Networks (TNNs), which are a type of deep learning model, have transformed the field of natural language processing (NLP) and other sequential data tasks by applying self-attention and enabling a process that happens in parallel.

Attention is a mechanism in deep learning approaches and it enables models to emphasize different parts of the input sequence with different importance features. In an attentive neural network, the model decides on the importance of each part of the input sequence during the production process and then singles the attending elements that contain the relevant information.

In translation, this paper is on English-to-Malayalam translation using TNN encoder-decoder architecture. The architecture uses positional encodings to feed context-related vectors that are used to produce accurate translations. This study utilizes the Samanantar corpus dataset, an open-access parallel corpus for Indic languages. This experiment will assess the competence of TNNs in the processing of complex translations. Now at the end of the experiment, the training loss will be calculated and plotted to observe the efficiency of this modality.

Moreover, the article examines how TNNs can be used for image generation with the aid of a process called stable diffusion. To accomplish this purpose, a Hugging Face model

was used. Thus, we could also carry out the integration of TNNs with the diffusion model demonstrating the image generation from both a text prompt and vice versa. Through the implementation of the applications, the study intends to explore TNNs' capability in terms of image generation.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Transformer architecture developed by Vaswani et al. (2017) revolves around attention mechanisms and does not demand recurrent or convolutional layers described as self-attention. The Transformer has intrigued many researchers in the NLP domain by delivering superior performance in various tasks.

Firstly the most crucial element of Transformer is its self-attention mechanism through which the model can define how crucial different words in the input sentence are while generating the output sentence. Instead of considering this succession of words as a flat straight line during which the previous word is not considered, the model learns how to extend the sequence in a more structured manner.

The Transformer, which is based on encoder-decoder architecture, mainly includes the encoder part that processes the input format and the decoder which is responsible for generating the output sequence. Each layer in the encoder and decoder hierarchies is formed of both multi-head attention layers and feed-forward neural networks.

One of the main advantages of the Transformer is its parallelism. The attention mechanism is what enables the processing to be uniform for each word in the input. It is the preservation of the model context that allows parallel processing at vastly higher speeds compared to sequential processing of words, which is a restriction of RNN.

Xiong et al. (2020) studied all the issues on layer normalization and how to use it normally in Transformer structure, which is very effective for Transformer stability and performance. Layer normalization is for normalizing the amount of input to each layer of a neural network that builds stability to the training process and promotes the model's capacity for generalization.

The authors examined varied layer normalization methods from their one-layer normalization up to the different statistical variants of layer normalization. They tested them on those variants again on different tasks of translation; and used the Transformer model to run that.

Their results demonstrate that at times the justification of normalization can be highly essential when the performance of the Transformer is concerned. It was demonstrated that the Layer-wise statistics, computed over the whole training set,

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11525743](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11525743)

ISBN: 978-93-5906-046-0@2024, Dept. of Computer Applications, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

rather than the batch-wise statistics, are beneficial for performance improvement. Furthermore, they found that the depth-wise separable convolution with layer normalization before the nonlinear activation function gave better results than with layer normalization after the nonlinear activation function.

Ho et al. (2020) proposed the denoising diffusion probabilistic models, a class of generative models that employ a diffusion process to create high-fidelity images. In contrast to the generative models like variational autoencoders (VAEs), which directly produce the images from random noise vectors, the diffusion model works iteratively by adding noise and then removing it to generate images with high resolution.

The fundamental principle of denoising diffusion models is representing the diffusion phenomenon as a sequence of stages, in which using each successive stage the model magnifies the initial error and then recoup the missing pattern before progressing to the next step. The model learns to predict the parameters of the noise model at each step in addition to the denoising function. The result is a blackened image that is as close as possible to the original.

It was Ronneberger et al. (2015) who developed the U-Net architecture which is a CNN (CNN stands for convolutional neural network) designated for biomedical image segmentation. Its significance lies in the symmetry of its encoding-decoding structure that enables to define the segmentation of the images pixel-wise.

The U-Net architecture consists of two branches i. e. an encoder and decoder. The block next to the contracting path is analogous to a conventional CNN model that can help to understand the context of the input image. The extended path is used for the exact determination by using convolutions in the place for the sub-sampling, to upsample the feature maps from the down-sampling path.

Hence, along with this, U-Net makes use of the skip connections from the corresponding layers of the contracting and the expansive paths. These shortcuts help the network to preserve the represented valuable information from the early layers and also result in improving the segmentation accuracy, more particularly, the detail of small objects.

Baltrušaitis et al. (2019) succinctly explain the MML (Multimodal Machine Learning) approach which is a field on its own. The primary aim in this area is to develop algorithms capable of processing and understanding data presented as text, audio, video, and images. The article underscores that MML is a key technology in areas such as machine translation, natural language processing, computer vision, and speech recognition where converting data among multilingual information sources is the typical operation.

The writers begin by explaining why MML is required by pointing out the need for models that can integrate information on different modalities. The models should be impervious to any adverse environmental conditions. Data coming from various sources is the subject because of heterogeneity, alignment, and scalability. See how the research in the field is pushed to tackle these challenges.

The paper will then undergo a detailed investigation into different MML approaches and will categorize them according to the type of modalities utilized (such as text, images, audio) or the type of fusion methods adopted (such as

early fusion, late fusion, or hybrid fusion). Decisive points of the authors are indicated about the areas of minor and major flaws of different approaches as well as foundations of the latest research and advancements in the field of MML.

Lastly, contributions of MML to multimedia retrieval, sentiment analysis, and human-computer interaction will be presented, allowing to demonstration of a wide area of applications where MML methods were successfully utilized. The authors also mention the datasets and metrics of evaluation that are common in this field of research, thus entailing the provision of insights about measuring and evaluating multimodal models.

III. METHODOLOGY

1. English to Malayalam Translation

The initial step of the model is Attention mechanisms (Scaled Dot-Product Attention) which is used to calculate the attention weight determining the sequence position and relevance.

Due to the lack of inherent context throughout the sequence, positional encodings are augmented on the input embeddings so that the information related to each element's position in the sequence can be retrieved. Their sum plays the role of the key in the Multi-Head Attention Layer, which extends the input embeddings into multiple subspaces, making it possible to focus on different elements of the sequence at the same time and uncover intricate dependencies.

Layer Normalization scales the output values in each layer to a common denominator thus contributing to a smoother training and making generalization easier. Non-position Feed-Forward Networks are employed exclusively for each position within a sequence basis, making the model as a whole suitable to process the information sequentially more appropriately.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the Transformer model architecture.

2. Stable Diffusion

The variational autoencoder (VAE) architecture encompasses convolutional layers, residual blocks, and an attention mechanism to take out features, and show complex patterns and dependencies between input and latent represented.

At the encoder side, convolutional layers are used to extract features, those are subsequently taken for by residual blocks to optimally capture complex features. Downsizing, results in the loss of pixel values and their number, which, then allows for more abstract feature generation. Group normalization helps stabilize training and SiLU activation function becomes successful at the end of each normalization.

The last convolutional layer then produces tensors which are considered as a means and a log variance of a latent distribution. Noise is injected into the latent representation for regularization while the context is padded by asymmetric padding so that the information loss can be avoided. The random process of the variational autoencoder has a variance that is clamped, to make it numerically stable, and the standard deviation that is necessary for scaling of the added noise to the latent representation is estimated.

In the decoder, convolutional layers act as a reverse process to reconstruct the image from the latent representation while residual blocks facilitate the capturing of complex features effectively. Normally, a group normalization is done and the SiLU activation function is used. Upsampling is used when spatial dimensions are expanded to aid in image reconstruction at the original dimensions. A block of attention integrates global data into the decoder to reduce the rate of errors during reconstructions.

In the last convolutional layer, the feature dimension is treated as an image channel by the decoder, and the scaling factor added by the encoder is removed, so the values can be brought into the original range.

The attention mechanisms cover both self-attention and cross-attention to ensure the dependencies in the input image and the latent representation are incorporated. This information may be communicated from the input image to the latent representation or vice versa.

Due to the conglomeration of those characteristics, the RNN-based model is capable of reconstructing high-quality pictures out of latent representations hence it is also good at image reconstruction and representation learning. It also relies on a simple version of a CLIP (Contrastive Language-Image pre-training) model consisting of text embedding and transformer-like layers. The CLIP model is structured into three main components: CLIPEmbedding, CLIPLayer, and CLIP will be the topic.

CLIP embedding deals with introducing the token and positional embeddings, used in CLIP. It resorts to an embedding layer for token embeddings and comes with a trainable positional embedding matrix. It is this part that will guarantee that the model is capable of giving both token and positional information, both are important factors in the correct understanding of the input text.

CLIPLayer is a single-layer component of the CLIP model. It encompasses a pre-attentional normalization layer, a self-attention mechanism that employs a causal mask to avoid

attending to future symbols, and a feedforward layer. The self-attention mechanism allows the model to highlight what parts of the text are the most important, while the feedforward layer is meant to process this information.

CLIP designates the architecture of the entire model incorporating embedding layer and CLIP layers. The word embedding layer extracts the inputs as embeddings, and the model applies the CLIP layers sequentially to process the embeddings in detail. With this architecture, CLIP can learn representations of image text at a semantic level, which makes it possible to perform tasks like matching images and texts and classification of images and texts.

The UNET architecture is the network designed with the encoder-decoder structure with the addition of attention and residual blocks. The first operation of the encoder processes an image input through a set of layers, where each layer can either be a residual block or an attention block. These blocks are used for obtaining and processing the features from the input image. The encoder then includes skip connections that save spatial information and contribute to the reconstruction process.

The bottleneck part further extracts features from the encoder before the decoding process. The decoder then upsamples the bottleneck output and concatenates it with the matching skip connection from the encoder. This technique incrementally removes the focal plane until the final spatial resolution is obtained. Decoder layers also alternate between residual blocks and attention blocks to keep a balance between feature extraction and context comprehension.

Figure 2. UNET.

Furthermore, UNET architecture involves a TimeEmbedding module which defines a single input time value having a higher dimensional space using linear layers, where SiLU activation is used. This module improves the model's proficiency in temporal information, on which the time factor may hold pivotal value for tasks with the time spectrum becomes the factor.

UNET_OutputLayer module applies the last processing operation to the output of the UNET to get the required output format. It contains the construction of a group normalization unit followed by the SiLU activation and a convolutional layer in the end, which can be applied to a variety of tasks, such as semantic segmentation or image inpainting.

The generate function presented in the solution is a part of the bigger image generation stack through the use of a

Diffusion Probabilistic Model (DDPM). Our pipeline starts with an initialization of the CLIP model which is then represented to generate context embeddings from the textual prompts. Thus, it also includes the input image encoding into the latent representation, stochastic noise creation using the diffusion model, and the final latent space representation decoding into images. In the course of the whole pipeline, it utilizes attention mechanisms within the UNET system to present more accurate and specific images.

DDPM uses the DDPMsampler class to sample noise which is an essential element in its generation of images. The class is initialized with parameters such as num_training_steps, beta_start, and beta_end, which will be used to compute alpha and beta for each training step. These values give an idea about the spread of noise at different training stages. Moreover, class control of the number of inference steps sets the granularity of the noise sampling during inference.

While the sampling is going on, the DDPMsampler class calculates the noise distribution's variance using the computed alphas and betas. This randomness is used to add noise to the latent outputs, and the style of the image might be changed. In the 'noise strength' of the class one could regulate the amount of noise added so that the output image would resemble the input image to a greater extent.

A generative adversarial model uses UNET with attention and residual blocks to handle image data and context vectors in the complete pipeline. CLIP is an example of a model that is used for encoding textual prompts into context embeddings, which are then concatenated with the latent embeddings of given images. The noise sampling property of the DDPMsampler unit fits in with the features of the UNET architecture and raises the level of the quality of the generated images by their begotten context awareness. Ultimately, such a framework indicates a holistic process of image generation, which involves many components to yield realistic and context-aware outputs.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

1. Translation

The process of creating an English to Malayalam Transformer model involves a series of stages as follows: defining the vocabulary for both languages, preparing the datasets, establishing the transformer model's architecture, and finally training the model.

Vocabularies for English and Malayalam are defined as START_TOKEN, PADDING_TOKEN, and END_TOKEN before proceeding. These markers delimit sentence beginnings and endings and provide padding for sentences with different lengths.

The dataset is read from local files in which one line consisting of one English and one Malayalam sentence is present. The number is limited to save training time. The sentence is then processed to remove the newline characters and make sure they are of a length less than the maximum sequence length.

The Transformer model implementation is done by utilizing the given Transformer class that contains the encoder as well as decoder parts. A DataLoader is used to train the model efficiently by having it process batches of sentences.

The masks will be applied to padding tokens during training and attend to the past not the future tokens after the training is over.

```

-----
Iteration 36700 : 1.1432037353515625
English: rain again?
Malayalam Translation: വീണ്ടും പ്രളയസാധ്യതയോ?
Malayalam Prediction: പിണ്ടും പറയായേഴ്യാതമയോ?
Evaluation translation (should we go to the mall?): നിന്നക്ക് എന്തെ പറയുന്നു.<END>
-----
Precision: 0.0
Recall: 0.0
Accuracy: 0.0
F1 Score: 0
-----
Iteration 36800 : 1.2685678005218506
English: one, two, three, four.
Malayalam Translation: ഒന്ന്, രണ്ട്, മൂന്ന്, നാല്, അഞ്ച്.
Malayalam Prediction: അന്ന് ഒണ്ട് അറന്ന് ഒംംല ഒത്ത്.
Evaluation translation (should we go to the mall?): നിന്നക്ക് നിന്നക്ക് പോകാമോ?<END>
-----
Precision: 0.0
Recall: 0.0
    
```

Figure 3. Training of translation model.

In each iteration, the training loop applies the dataset for a specified number of epochs where it calculates the loss and updates the model parameters with optimization by the Adam optimizer. The loss is calculated by the nn.CrossEntropyLoss function, which regards the predicted and actual tokens and the special processing for padding tokens. The optimizer does the adjusting of the model's parameters according to the calculated loss and thus the model can eventually become more accurate in the translation of English to Malayalam sentences.

The loss metrics are saved in a pickle every time an evaluation is performed. The next step is to save the trained model to a pickle file for future applications.

2. Stable Diffusion

It uses the CLIP model for text-to-image generation and image-to-image processing.

As for the text-to-image generation, the code takes a textual prompt as input to describe the image content and gives an image that is described in the text. For example, "A dog with sunglasses, wearing a comfy hat, looking at the camera." The input is tokenized with the CLIP tokenizer and the CLIP model is used to generate the image. The generated picture is then displayed and saved to the file.

In processing of image to image, a code picks an input image, e.g. a picture of a dog, and turns it according to a specified textual prompt. The prompt might contain the transformation directions, for example, "highly detailed, ultra-sharp, cinematic" which are utilized to steer the process. The CLIP model is applied to the input picture with the transformed picture being displayed and saved on the file.

In both cases, the CLIP model is exploited to cover up the gap between text and images which allows generation and conversion of images based on textual input.

3. Multimodal Implementation

For translation, the application takes the English sentence as input and the Transformer model is used to translate it into Malayalam. Tokenization of the sentence to be translated,

masking for padding and looking forward, and iteration to predict the next token in the translated sentence until the end token is encountered is the translation process.

Text-to-image generation in the application emphasizes picture generation from a given text prompt. This is accomplished with a pipeline that is fed with a text prompt and uses a set of models like encoder-decoder architecture to produce the image. The generated image is saved and displayed to the user as a result.

One key feature here is image-to-image translation, where an input image is transformed into another image based on the given strength parameter. By using this process, the input image is loaded, the pipeline for image-to-image generation is applied, and the output image to be viewed by the user is saved.

The application uses Flask for the routing and template display. It consists of paths that implement the primary functionalities, namely translation, text-to-image, and image-to-image generation. Following the choice of an option, the application completes the request and generates the output as well as renders the result template including the translated text, generated images, or error messages.

Consequently, the application employs pre-trained models along with pipelines to provide users with a text translation, an image generation based on the text prompt, and an image transformation by a customized strength level within a user-designed web interface. Additionally, by employing the same pipelining, the application can use all three functions consecutively, thereby achieving multimodal capability since a single text input will allow the user to generate an image and using the generated image, generate a related image and display it with the translation of the text as the caption.

V. RESULT

In the case of the translation model training, the paper has successfully implemented a Transformer model for English-to-Malayalam translation. After setting up the vocabulary for both languages, preprocessing the dataset, and defining the Transformer model architecture, you trained the model using a DataLoader to efficiently process batches of sentences. After training the model was outputted as a pickle file that can be imported and used to dynamically translate new user inputs as shown in figure 4.

```
Enter an English sentence (type 'exit' to quit): hello  
Malayalam Translation: ഹലോ.<END>  
Enter an English sentence (type 'exit' to quit): how  
Malayalam Translation: നീങ്ങുക കറന്നോ?<END>
```

Figure 4. Result of Translation

Meanwhile, the text-to-image and image-to-image have generated high quality from the input thereby proving the effectiveness of models as elaborated in figures 5, 6, and 7. The next step of the process was to compile the effectiveness of the model during training which is achieved by calculating the training loss through the many iterations it underwent

Figure 5. Result of Text to Image

Figure 6. Input of Image to Image

Figure 7. Output of Image to Image

The data compiled during training of the translation model showcases how there is a drastic decrease in a loss at the beginning of the training and later fluctuates between 1 and 2 for the majority of iterations while some go below 0.5. This

showcases the effectiveness of transformer neural networks in Natural Language Processing tasks.

Figure 8. Training loss vs Iterations

To create a multimodal setup, the paper employs a Flaskweb application to allow users to use all three features separately as well as together. The result is that users can input a text and get a translation, a corresponding image, and an alternative image for the same. This is achieved by pipelining the text input into the translation and text-to-image models and the result of the text-to-image model being used as the input of the image-to-image model. This is illustrated in the figures given below.

Figure 9. UI with various options

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

For future work, a lot of directions are quite attractive. First, the accuracy of the translation can be improved more through the perfection of the training process, the investigation of different structures, and the application of more linguistic elements. Furthermore, we can decrease the processing time with the help of optimization methods such as model parallelism or hardware acceleration. Finally, reducing the loss rate even further with the help of hyperparameters fine-tuning, and model regularization can also lead to better and more fine-tuned outputs.

Additionally, multilanguage translation capability and integration of more models will make this tool more versatile thus it will have many applications like automatic multilingual article generation which will have of great impact on news writing and blogging.

VIII. REFERENCES

- [1] Ashish Vaswani, Noam Shazeer, Niki Parmar, Jakob Uszkoreit, Llion Jones, Aidan N. Gomez, Łukasz Kaiser, and Illia Polosukhin. 2017. Attention is all you need. In Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NIPS'17). Curran Associates Inc., Red Hook, NY, USA, 6000–6010.
- [2] Ruibin Xiong, Yunchang Yang, Di He, Kai Zheng, Shuxin Zheng, Chen Xing, Huishuai Zhang, Yanyan Lan, Liwei Wang, and Tie-Yan Liu. 2020. On-layer normalization in the transformer architecture. In Proceedings of the 37th International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML'20), Vol. 119. JMLR.org, Article 975, 10524–10533.
- [3] Jonathan Ho, Ajay Jain, and Pieter Abbeel. 2020. Denoising diffusion probabilistic models. In Proceedings of the 34th International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NIPS '20). Curran Associates Inc., Red Hook, NY, USA, Article 574, 6840–6851.
- [4] Ronneberger, O., Fischer, P. and Brox, T., 2015. U-

net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation. In Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention– MICCAI 2015: 18th International Conference, Munich, Germany, October 5-9, 2015, Proceedings, Part III 18 (pp. 234- 241). Springer International Publishing. T. Baltrušaitis, C. Ahuja and L. -P. Morency, "Multimodal Machine Learning: A Survey and Taxonomy," in IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence, vol. 41, no. 2, pp. 423-443, 1 Feb. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TPAMI.2018.2798607. keywords: {Speech recognition; Visualization; Media; Speech; Multimedia communication; Streaming media; Hidden Markov models; Multimodal; machine learning; introductory; survey},